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AI visuals: A problem, a solution, or more of the same?

While some argue that AI imagery can be a force for democratisation, others worry that it is simply repackaging harmful stereotypes.

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Editor's note: This column, **Decolonise How?** charts efforts towards more ethical reporting of humanitarian crises.

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“We are a small NGO; we cannot afford to commission photographers like the big international ones do,” Malik*, a communications officer based in western Europe, told me when I spoke with him for my research on the use of AI imagery in the aid and development sector. “NGO imagery has always been more or less manufactured, and people use stock images all the time,” he continued. “How is an AI image any different from that? I am not sure.”

Instead of photography, Malik’s team relies entirely on **MidJourney**, a popular text-to-image AI generator, to create striking photorealistic portraits. “For €50 a month, we can create unlimited images as if they were created by the best photographers,” he attested. “It gets us much-needed visibility in competing for the attention of viewers.”

While it's difficult to estimate the extent of AI imagery use by NGOs, a **survey of 378 individuals by the Charity Excellence Framework** suggests that 3% of respondents used DALL·E and 2% MidJourney for image outputs. This is by no means the full picture: The **Joseph Rowntree Foundation** estimates that only 15% of the organisations that use generative AI in their outputs actually disclose it.

And the use of such images isn't limited to small, cash-strapped organisations.

Leading charities and humanitarian agencies are also **increasingly turning to AI**. "I see AI imagery in my feed nearly every day," admitted James*, a West African communications expert based in North America. "Sometimes even in the NGO reports," he added, highlighting the rise of so-called **AI slop** and its strong influence on marketing practices **across the African continent**.

Many organisations are concerned about the trust-eroding consequences of using synthetic imagery, with memories of the **backlash against Amnesty International** using AI to depict protests in Colombia still fresh in mind. Beyond the risk of misrepresenting reality, an especially alarming development is the use of AI imagery by scammers running **fake campaigns** and by so-called briefcase NGOs with little, if any, actual presence on the ground.

Predictably, globally influential tech companies, such as Adobe, are looking to cash in on this demand. And in contrast with Malik's portraits, much of what is on sale can be horrifying.

For a one-off fee or a monthly subscription, users can purchase photorealistic AI images (and videos) of a young presumed African **child crouching to drink from a filthy puddle**, a presumed African man screaming with anguish against a backdrop of crumbling shacks and open sewers, an emaciated child in rags begging for food, a poor **Black boy covered in mud**, a **white saviour saving presumed African children**, or a **child bride** next to a husband four times her age, among hundreds of other visuals with disturbing captions. While some of these images have been deleted following **press reports**, others remain online for sale.

All this highlights a growing tension: Does AI imagery allow for democratisation and even decolonisation of visual communication, or does it simply repackage damaging stereotypes and unethical practices more cheaply? Or is it doing both?

AI feeds off humanitarian tropes

In the humanitarian and aid sector, where there is neither consensus nor enforceable rules on the use of AI imagery, arguments can be made for both sides of the debate.

On one hand, AI imagery can be framed as decolonial, from an ethical marketing perspective. It allows small grassroots NGOs to generate visually striking images fast and at relatively little cost, while removing the logistical and ethical burden of travelling and securing consent from photography subjects, and retaining the **nuanced control of the outputs**. In this sense, it could appear, at glance, to advance the goal of widening space for bottom-up narratives, especially coming from the Majority World.

On the other hand, a counterargument is that AI substitutes reality-capturing photojournalism with fakery and thus revamps the legacy of colonial misrepresentation.

Tapping into these discussions, my research suggests that rather than framing AI as a unique rupture and paradigm shift, it would be helpful to view synthetic imagery as a lens into unresolved systemic issues and colonial imprints. AI does not exist in a vacuum. To make humanitarian-style images, AI learns from the existing stock of humanitarian imagery and the biases embedded in it. That corpus of images and stereotypes was produced by photographers over decades; arguably centuries, if we trace the lineage back to colonial photography and artwork. This is especially the case for **the white saviour** trope.

Illustrating this, a communication expert at a major humanitarian organisation based in western Europe told me they had been approached by a major transnational corporation seeking to purchase their entire visual archive for AI training. Another expert at a different organisation was fearful that their publicly accessible collection – already saturated with stereotypes – had likely been scraped without

consent. This might partially explain the presence of the white saviour bias in generative **outputs**. After all, AI images are statistically averaged and **flattened** products of past representations. One day, a pixel-by-pixel investigation might uncover the precise traces of images reassembled to construct humanitarian-style AI visuals.

What becomes of consent?

Is AI-mediated bypassing of consent a fundamental rupture? “I can generate images of a particular community without travelling there; also, it helps to anonymise the vulnerable people,” said Ababuo*, a communications officer in a West African NGO, echoing Malik’s emphasis on saving time and money.

Ababuo is not alone in this justification: The World Health Organization **used the same reasoning** of protection of vulnerability to defend its own AI-generated campaign against crops-for-profit, as did the UN for using **AI-generated avatars** to speak on behalf of people subjected to the wartime sexual violence.

Historically speaking, consent for photography did not exist as a general practice even 30 years ago. Current communication standards demand the evidence of consent with little, if any, reflection directed as to *how* the consent was obtained. To make the situation worse, it is common knowledge – if often swept under the rug – that power imbalances between the photographer, who can be perceived as a gateway to aid, and the subject produce **undue inducement and coercion**.

This is a structural problem that cannot be easily mitigated without addressing the underlying socioeconomic inequalities. In this sense, AI merely perpetuates longstanding practices of how coloniality helps bypass or manufacture genuine consent, rather than introducing anything fundamentally new.

From photographers’ briefs to AI prompts

The same seems to be true about the argument that AI imagery somehow is uniquely detached from real contexts, that it introduces fakery through text-to-image practices. Someone at an organisation

needs to prompt what image they want to see (e.g. 'an empowered African woman', or 'a starving African child'), without seeing the realities on the ground.

This development is not unique to AI: For decades, commissioned photographers have been receiving briefs — prescriptive bullet points detailing what a photographer needs to capture and what to avoid, and how to encounter local realities more generally.

Briefs are often written by communications departments based in the Global North, and they essentially pre-script what the reality looks like. Old-school briefs, as products of their time, generally prompted misery and death, while the contemporary ones tend to hyperfocus on happiness and empowerment as predefined themes, often forcing photographers to either stage or selectively focus on such scenes locally.

Below, for instance, are extracts from two briefs enacted in the Majority World in the past 10 years, shown with the permission of two commissioned photographers who executed them:

Brief on children and young adults with disabilities

- ‘Hero’ shots of young people with disabilities, at home, at work, with products they have made, in the workplace, etc (positive, empowering shots’
- ‘Observational shots of course participant getting ready for work/ doing tasks around the home – capture small details such as personal grooming, signs of nerves or excitement, etc.’
- ‘Observational shots of course participant interacting with family members, possibly family members saying goodbye to them as they leave for work’
- ‘Portrait with eyes to camera of participant at home (both interior and exterior)’
- ‘Observational shots of course participant travelling to work – full length and mid shots’
- ‘Shots of equipment given to participants to help them – eg white cane, calendar box, special tactile objects to help them better communicate, etc’

Brief on food insecurity

- ‘Inhabitants are hungry and cannot get to help’
- ‘Hungry children’
- ‘Severely stunted children’
- ‘A mother with a child suffering from extreme severe acute malnutrition (SAM)’
- ‘A mother who has walked for days to bring her starving/malnourished child to the clinic’
- ‘A child on the brink of death’

Each bullet point became a visual. Photographers working with the communication departments are precursors for the generative engines; briefs are in fact proto-AI prompts, and AI prompts are post-briefs, all existing in the continuum of text-to-image practices.

Photography briefs are usually accompanied by past images from a media library as points of reference to be reproduced *de novo*. AI adds a twist to it: “We generated images in ChatGPT to brainstorm with designers and photographers about what images to take in real life – like to test and coordinate a campaign across multiple creators,” explained Karabo*, a communications officer for a large organisation based in Southern Africa, highlighting how AI can shape the inner workings of communications.

Beyond the questions of truthfulness, what is the fundamental difference between a photographer receiving a past image or an AI image to be recreated in real life? This exemplifies a much broader

tension between marketing and photojournalism: AI is not blurring it; it is making the underlying contradictions apparent.

“We actually took real images and modified them with AI,” said Ganda*, the head of communications for an East Africa-based organisation.

“The people – their faces – were real, but the surroundings were fully adjusted. The result was beautiful.” Despite the perceived attractiveness of such imagery, Ganda and their team decided not to publish such real-synthetic images: “People who gave consent to be photographed never consented for AI edits,” she added.

Now, with just a few words and clicks, one can simply select an area of an image and describe the desired changes using tools such as Midjourney’s editing function or Adobe Photoshop’s generative fill. Tears – even people – can be added or erased; rubbish or logos can appear or vanish. Ganda’s experience illustrates the ongoing outcry that AI is actively blurring the boundary between marketing and photojournalism, thereby colonising the representation.

Yet there is nothing fundamentally new in these developments.

Humanitarian and aid photography has long been shaped by the gaze of Western – often white – male photojournalists who “encountered” the suffering of the Other in response to the briefs and training, producing cascades of dehumanisation and familiar visual tropes: the white saviour **poverty porn**, **suffering bodies**, and **speechless emissaries**.

Mounting criticism of **parachute journalism** eventually led to the rise of marketing and communications departments designed to moderate problematic imagery while ensuring that outputs could still compete with mainstream advertising for public attention. This, in turn, entrenched the sector’s reliance on briefs, which oftentimes explicitly state which objects should be included or avoided in communities, resulting in a manual modification of scenes, or selective representation. In other words, AI does not mark the beginning of the blurring between marketing and photojournalism – it is merely its latest manifestation.

“One click away from going live”

Janine, head of a large Western European NGO with global outreach, highlights another worry. “We made a decision to withdraw an AI-generated campaign targeting communities in need,” she said as she showed me visuals featuring West Asian families created in January 2024, which I show here with consent and anonymisation:

“It was one click away from going live, but we were concerned of being perceived as culturally insensitive, so we withdrew it,” she explained. It raises an important point: There is no guarantee that other synthetic visuals will not contain subtle distortions that may slip through internal review yet trigger backlash once released in target communities.

This, again, strictly speaking, is not an AI problem: Questions of visual representation emerged long ago, when photographers entered communities with little, if any, cultural understanding of the contexts they depicted. AI merely accelerates and intensifies this existing dilemma.

Following James’s concern about encountering AI imagery in his feed, I tested the search function on LinkedIn by looking for image-containing posts using stereotypical categories such as “aid”, “collaborative partnership”, “hunger”, and “empowerment”, among many others.

This heuristic experiment yielded more than 100 AI-generated images published in the NGO and aid industry space in recent months – both by individuals and organisations – generated with Meta AI, Grok, ChatGPT/DALL·E and Midjourney. Strikingly, most of them were posted by people and organisations in the Majority World (though none were created by those I interviewed). To protect the anonymity of the posters, I reverse-engineered the most striking examples of such

imagery (AI to AI), capturing the overall visual grammar of the images encountered.

Is it really surprising that people based in the Global South would use AI to reproduce imagery widely recognised as unethical? Not really. Most humanitarian and aid imagery targeted a Global North audience – some upper-class or middle-class Westerner who would donate to save poor children upon seeing images catering to their sentimentality. This imagery is exactly what the NGOs, even those based in the Majority World, have been systemically expected to produce to survive in the humanitarian system.

Given the rapid pace of technological advancement in the last few years, it is likely that an increasing number of people and organisations will gain access to ultra-photorealistic AI tools that continue to improve in capability. While it is already clear that shrinking budgets are pushing many NGOs to experiment with synthetic imagery, the future of such in humanitarian communications is uncertain. It could turn out to be little more than a passing fad. Or it could become seamlessly woven into everyday routines under the banner of “ethical AI”, with organisations training their own customised models on carefully curated datasets that will conveniently circumvent the history of the industry.

My own – admittedly uncomfortable, perhaps even white-saviorish – conclusion is that attempting to decolonise AI or humanitarian communication without confronting entrenched socio-material inequalities and biases risks reducing decolonisation to a **mere**

metaphor. Clearly, simply briefing or prompting for images of empowered women and children is not enough.

**Names have been changed due to the sensitivity of discussing this topic.*

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